

Supplementary Material 1. Taxonomic specialists and the fungal groups that they reviewed for this work.

Fungal groups reviewed for this work	Taxonomic specialists
Agaric and boletoid fungi	Milagro Mata Hidalgo
Ascomycota (not lichenized)	Melissa Mardones
Basal fungi	Melissa Mardones
Cybertruffle	David Minter
Gasteroid fungi	Milagro Mata Hidalgo
“Heterobasidiomycetes” fungi	Melissa Mardones
Lichenized fungi	Loengrin Umaña Tenorio
Pathogenic fungi in crops	María del Milagro Granados Montero
Polyporoid and crustose fungi	Armando Ruiz-Boyer and Julieta Carranza Velázquez
Rust fungi	Melissa Mardones
Smut fungi	Meike Piepenbring
